

D5.1 – Report on data encoding- integration-processing needs of CH stakeholders

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Abstract

This report is part of the work planned in the project *PNRR PE 5 "CHANGES"*, and specifically in Spoke 5 "Science and Technologies for Sustainable Diagnostics for Cultural Heritage", WP5 "Digital technologies, AI/ML solutions, chemometric methods supporting data-driven Heritage".

It implements one of the results planned in the project: *R5.1 – Study of CH stakeholders' needs concerning data encoding/integration/processing – M12* and constitutes one of the Deliverables: *D5.1–Report on data encoding/integration/processing needs of CH stakeholders*.

The scope of this report is to collect, discuss, and organize the needs of our stakeholders (museum curators, conservators, restorers, art historians, ...), to highlight how they need support in terms of enabling digital data types, digitization processes, and digital platforms/tools. The results of this preliminary study will steer the design of the tools and technologies developed in Spoke5-WP5.

The Cultural Heritage (CH) context is very broad, both in terms of preservation goals and subjects (ranging from a small artifact to an entire building, up to an archaeological site or an entire city) and in terms of research/conservation questions (which, in turn, often require different representation approaches, media, scales, and accuracies). For this reason, we have first to introduce some concepts and distinctions between the different digital approaches to CH management, and then we will present the results of a questionnaire aimed at collecting information and needs from potential stakeholders. The final goal is to use this knowledge to guide the process of designing new digital tools aimed at supporting our community.

Representing heritage with digital formats - What and how?

The recent progress of digital technologies (archives, visual media, interactive tools) gives us a very wide set of instruments to support CH stakeholders, some of them designed ad hoc, following explicit CH requirements, but also many others inherited by other application contexts.

The European Commission has been advocating for the development of new tools and practices to establish digital support as a standard approach in CH activities for several years. The Commission Recommendation on digitization, online accessibility, and digital preservation of cultural material (2011/711/EU), endorsed by the Council in 2012, represents a milestone in digital cultural policy. A recent report [EC19] surveyed the progress of this evolution process, examining how member states are planning, organizing, and monitoring the digitization of CH. Despite active digitization efforts by various member states, the objective of fundamentally transforming CH activities into digital procedures remains largely unfulfilled. One contributing factor to this challenge is the existing deficiency in supporting platforms that facilitate the archival of digital data and their integration into stakeholders' activities. This is further compounded by the absence of tools specifically tailored to meet the requirements and preferences of the particular community involved. Moreover, digital CH data are often still kept closed. Opening them to the public domain to enable data reuse is still a major issue and a goal to be accomplished [EC2019].

The objective of this section is to establish the foundation for the discussion in the second part of the report and elucidate certain nomenclature and concepts, albeit in a concise manner.

The first important concept to introduce here is the one of **digital representation**. The evolution of digital instruments brought us a very wide arsenal of *representation media and schema* that allows to build digital replicas of the object of interest.

CH is a very complex domain. We do not have only a single reference object (as it is the human body in medical studies) but many highly differentiated CH subjects of potential interest for study or conservation purposes. It is not just a matter of size/scale (a small coin or a jewel, a statue, some architectural elements, a building, an entire city). It is also a matter of constituent materials, each one presenting different appearance and degradation processes.

Given the very wide context, it cannot exist a single reference model or preferred digital media for the representation of all CH assets. Given the spectrum of options available for representing CH assets, the selection of the best-fitting media usually depends on both the characteristics of the specific CH asset and the specific conservation/research questions in the mind of the CH expert. We should always have in mind the main research/conservation questions when deciding on how to digitize and represent a specific artifact. This is somehow in contrast with the idea of digitizing to support multiple future actions; thus, endorsing the concept of data reuse which is at the base of the idea of performing massive CH digitization, archiving those results in FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) [WDA16] and open archives, to support a multitude of future applications. It is important to underline here that there is not a single unifying representation, but multiple potential media.

To provide specific examples, in cases where the emphasis is on characterizing the conservation status of a painted surface, practitioners frequently opt to digitize it using a simple 2D medium, such as an [high-resolution] image. Subsequently, they gather or reproject relevant information (annotations, outcomes of scientific investigations generating images, etc.) onto this pivotal 2D representation.

Alternatively, we might need to opt for a 3D representation medium if the shape characteristics of the artwork significantly impact its study. In such instances, encoding and representing the artwork's 3D features become essential. This is applicable to scenarios involving a complete three-dimensional object, like a sculpture, or even in cases where the artwork is typically perceived as a 2D element (such as frescoes or painted surfaces), where factors like cracks, partial detachments, or curvatures play a crucial role in the assessment and treatment phases.

Therefore, the focus should not be on selecting a single main media, but (1) planning digitization processes able to produce multiple representation media and (2) building software instruments that should make it very easy for the CH users to use multiple media, integrating them in the reasoning process (both based on visual interaction or supported by measuring or computing processes).

The concept of *reference media or model* is important, it depends on conservation/research questions, but it could change even in a short temporal framework (due to changes or evolution of the main research questions). Therefore, we should not focus on a single representation, but on multiple media which will allow us to encode and support the degree of complexity needed in CH applications.

Media used in CH applications.

Let us introduce some media classes that are quite common in CH applications:

- *2D images* are the main media to represent many artifacts (e.g., paintings on canvas/wood or frescoes, coins, and ancient walls). There are different incarnations of this type of data: the

usual RGB images, or the multispectral images (the ones encoding the light reflected by a surface while sampling only a specific wavelength [PCC20], often used to go beyond a paint layer);

- *2D Reflection Transformation Imaging (RTI) images* could be a compelling media when the focus of the investigation is the micro shape detail over (nearly-planar) surfaces, which can be encoded and reproduced quite well by sampling the reflection of light coming from many different directions [MGW01]; this data format allows to change the direction of the light incident over the object in real-time (i.e., at visualization time) to inspect fine details of the objects' surface;
- *Panoramic images* (or 360-degree images) are also very handy in encoding the visual appearance of an interior space (either a single room to a concatenated set of images supporting the virtual visit of complex architecture) or an external scene or panoramic view. An evolution of this media are the panoramic/360 videos;
- *3D geometric models* allow encoding the *shape* of an artifact, and not just its appearance (as in previous media); we can reuse this numeric information to support visualization (interactive synthesis of images produced for visualization/insight purposes), or simulations/computations which enable the solution of specific research queries. Models produced by sampling reality are usually quite accurate representations (accuracy is mandatory if a 3D model should be used to study and assess the status of an artwork);
- *Video* is a standard media also in CH, probably more used in dissemination than in conservation or study activities.

Let us call these media "**visual media**", to differentiate them from the usual *textual data* common in the archival process of CH knowledge (metadata, reports, gray literature, etc).

It is important also to underline that those media are not only used for the plain digitization of CH artifacts but are also the support for encoding and transmitting the results in many investigations or diagnostic analyses. Diagnostic analyses in some cases produce results related to a single location in space (a sampling point over the surface), but more and more often produce results covering a region of space, represented with 2D or 3D images encoding the results sampled. This usually enlarges a lot the spectrum of data associated with the artifact under study, pairing and integrating the data sampled in the initial digitization phase. In the activities concerning the study or conservation of CH assets, we have many pieces of information: visual data gathered to sample the state of an artwork and to produce its digital counterpart; more data (textual or visual) produced while studying it employing diagnostic instruments; visual data produced while sampling possible treatments; visual data produced to document the final results of restoration.

In some cases, a specific application not only induces the selection of a main reference media, but also leads to the selection of a specific platform used to manage the data. This happens more or less for all the visual media mentioned above.

For instance, in the case of 3D media, while the low-level data representation is usually based on triangulated surfaces, different approaches are endorsed in terms of SW solutions:

- a) In some cases, we use *interactive 3D systems* designed for the visualization and manipulation of high-resolution 3D models (for example the ones produced with 3D scanning of photogrammetry); those systems are often based on the usual manipulation approach of an artifact (trackball-based), and are frequently adopted in the case of single artifacts.
- b) *GIS (Geographic Information Systems) solutions* are often preferred for the representation of large archaeological contexts. The GIS approach has been initially developed to represent and

visualize large geographic spaces within a 2,5D space approach (2D map plus elevation) and has been more recently extended to full 3D representations. These approaches are very often used to represent archaeological sites (see for example the experiences of Lund University's Digital Archaeology Laboratory led by Nicolò Dell'Unto [DL22]).

- c) Another option is the adoption of *BIM (Building Information Modelling)* or *HBIM (Heritage BIM)* platforms used to represent buildings. Here the focus is the dual representation of the shape of a building as well as all the infrastructure components contained. More than an accurate, high-resolution representation of the shape (often impossible, since these platforms usually support hand-made 3D models produced with modeling systems), the advantage here is the tools for representing all the components and the services supporting the building.

It is important to underline that GIS and BIM systems have not been developed for CH users. They have a solid original application domain (management of land for GIS, design/construction of buildings in the case of BIM), and a few commercial companies have invested a considerable amount of money and resources in the development of these systems. Thus, in cases (b) and (c) we have very solid commercial products, usually very sophisticated and complex, but not designed having in mind the needs of CH stakeholders. The activity in the CH domain is mostly related to using those instruments in practical applications, rather than developing new GIS or HBIM platforms (since the work of extending or customizing commercial platforms is usually very complex or made impossible by Intellectual Property Rights - IPR limitations).

Conversely, some solutions in class (a) have been designed specifically to fulfill the needs of our CH community. The lack of SW companies interested in developing tools specific to the CH market (still perceived as a very small and not sufficiently rentable market) opens opportunities for the design of academic solutions. The focus of the SW design work in Changes-Spoke5 will be mostly oriented to this type of solutions.

Data mapping and integration

An important concept is therefore the capability of *mapping multiple data types on a common reference space*.

The mapping process, in the past devoted to the pure brain of the CH expert and part of the overall reasoning process, can be applied to different visual data. With 2D data, the organization of information into 2D data layers creates a sort of information cube (as it happens, for instance, with hyperspectral data). In this case, most of the difficulties consist in matching the information from the different 2D layers, sometimes produced by different techniques with different tools. Obviously, with 3D data, difficulties increase by one dimension.

In 3D graphics research, the concept of mapping was initially studied to enable the mapping of color data on top of 3D surfaces; mapping standard photographic images on digital 3D surfaces allowed to produce 3D models with both shape and reflection properties [RCM99, RCM02].

Nowadays, the concept of mapping is much more sophisticated, as in the management of CH data. It is not only restricted to the digitization phase but should enable work sessions where different sources of data would be mixed and integrated, by mapping them on a common representation space. This approach was already experimented in the management of CH data (see the seminal paper by the CNRS lab led by Livio de Luca [MVH18]). Unfortunately, it still presents an incomplete or missing endorsement in most CH systems/tools. There are many cases where the integration of data is a fundamental resource:

- The analysis of the status of an artifact performed by an expert produces a lot of knowledge, that is important to encode in the reference model that represents the object. This is the main scope of the *annotation* feature provided by many CH systems. But when multiple data are available to represent the artifact, it would be very handy if any single annotation could be automatically mapped and presented on every media representing the artifact. If we have both multiple images and 3D models representing the artifact, it would be handy if any single annotation would be automatically included and visually presented in any image/3D model that samples the same artifact location/region. This approach was pioneered in the AIOLI systems by CNRS [MVH18].
- Pre- and post-restoration status are often sampled with RGB images. Also in this case, the interactive mapping of those images on the related section of the 3D surface could be very handy to allow the curator (or even the public) to assess the effects of the restoration.
- In other cases, we need to sample and represent the status of the surface as well as of the interior of the artifact. An example was the monitoring of the *Ecce Homo* by Antonello da Messina (an oil painting over a wood table dated around 1470), where it was important to integrate the results of a CT scan (sampling the interior status of the wood support) with the status of the painted surface (sampled with high-resolution surface 3D scanning) [ARC21].

These and other examples of mapping or mixing media are reviewed in [Scop21].

Data sharing

Producing high-quality visual data is a resource-intensive endeavor, typically requiring the collaborative efforts of conservation institutions such as museums, libraries, and restoration labs, or arising within the framework of research projects spearheaded by academic institutions. Given that the availability of such data often results from significant institutional or professional investment, it is common to encounter restrictions or varying degrees of confidentiality in their utilization. Despite substantial infrastructure development and digitization projects funded by the European Union, the availability of high-quality digital replicas of CH assets suitable for scholarly research remains limited [CR19]. An imperative objective is to enhance accessibility and shareability of these data to facilitate their extensive reuse. The increased availability of data has the potential to catalyze the integration and solidification of digital technologies and tools within the CH domain. Establishing controlled access and safeguarding IPR is, therefore, a pivotal element for the widespread acceptance of a data-sharing paradigm.

Contemporary data sharing is predominantly facilitated through web technologies, incorporating user interfaces for both data ingestion and access. For instance, numerous initiatives have sought to streamline the sharing of 3D data, with many of the current resources for 3D repositories and viewers discussed in [CR20]. Some key takeaways from this literature include the observation that existing approaches are disparate, lacking guaranteed interoperability; deficiencies in managing *data provenance* and *metadata* are prevalent; and the majority primarily support interactive visualization, neglecting essential Cultural Heritage-related features such as annotations, measurements, similarity checks, and links to other sources of information or data.

Representative tools supporting web-based publication and sharing include *Sketchfab*¹ (3D) on the commercial side and, on the open-source academic side, the *3DHOP*² platform (3D) [PCD15], or the

¹ Sketchfab: <https://sketchfab.com/>

² 3DHOP: <https://www.3dhop.net/index.php>

associated *Visual Media Service*³ tool (multiple visual data) [PPD16]. Recent experiences, pioneered by Sketchfab and Visual Media Service, underscore the pivotal role of simplicity in the data ingestion phase for the success of a data-sharing tool. Ingestion processes should be as user-friendly as possible for data contributors, with ingested data subject to automated checks, potential enrichment, and transformation into formats conducive to efficient transmission and web-based visualization. Ease of interaction and user-friendliness are also critical factors in fostering widespread adoption. The Visual Media Service stands out as a rare platform that manages various data types (2D images, collections of 2D images, RTI images, 3D models), offering a consistent and uniform interface across all media browsers

Data sharing is also a key element for *sustainability*. Data formats evolve very fast, only a frequent reuse allows to keep the data readable and alive, preventing digital data obsolescence. On the other hand, the diffusion of shared repositories offers duplication of (often unexploited) digital representations of the same artifacts, whose accuracy is often unknown [Lom23]; this is in contrast with the need for certified quality digital replicas, well-documented and enhanced with metadata. A digital model can be aesthetically excellent, but at the same time without appropriate supporting metadata/paradata, transparent analysis and assessment, and citation of sources, it could not be the support to advance rigorous scholarly debate [Lom23]. Moreover, it is important to underline that not just the final processed data should be shared, but the raw data should also be accessible to allow running quality assessment, reprocessing the data (in case this should be needed in the future), or providing proper documentation on the data sources.

Annotation over visual data

Annotations represent a critical component within interactive systems, serving as a key feature that empowers experts to organize, store, and share knowledge by associating it with the digital representation of the artwork.

In the CH field, where the information to be managed is usually very heterogeneous and cannot be easily represented using conventional data management systems, annotation on visual data is particularly important.

The annotation task was initially applied to 2D images, on which the data was spatially distributed, creating a sort of information map (an approach that was then structured into GIS) [STL11]. However, the strong spatial nature of the CH data soon suggested that the information should be linked to the 3D representations [STL13].

Annotation over 3D data enables the linking of various types of information—ranging from concise text, extensive reports encoded within PDF files, tags, attribute values, images, and videos to recorded sounds or spoken streams—to specific locations or surface subsets of the artwork subject of study. Consequently, annotations achieve geo-referencing, tying information to precise portions of the 3D object [ABC17].

The process of defining annotations involves significant interaction, necessitating a structured dialogue between the users. And the supporting tool. The most straightforward form of geo-location is point-based annotation, wherein the user simply selects a point on the external surface of the artwork. More intricate selections involve subsets (e.g., isolating the hand or head of a statue), polylines (interconnected lines), or regions (closed polygonal portions of the surface). Various approaches can be employed to implement annotations, as detailed in the review provided in [PDC20].

³ Visual Media Service: <https://visual.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/>

Annotations also play a crucial role in introducing content selectively disclosed to users as they navigate the artwork and related data through an interactive installation/system.

As previously emphasized, offering diverse media types to represent different aspects of Cultural Heritage artworks is essential. Therefore, organizing and implementing annotations must facilitate the propagation of annotations defined on one media type to any other. An example of this approach is the AIOI restoration documentation system developed by CNRS [MVH18] in which, as mentioned before, annotations added to an image can be projected onto the 3D model and, consequently, onto any other image sampling the same area. The automatic inheritance of annotations across supported media types stands as a noteworthy advantage of this system.

Gathering Stakeholders' Requirements - Comparable Surveys

Collecting information on users' or stakeholders' needs is not a novel concept. Numerous preceding EC projects focused on the digital support of CH activities have committed significant efforts to explore the needs and preferences of the respective communities they support. Examples include the comprehensive state-of-the-art reviews conducted by projects such as ARIADNE Plus⁴ and Parthenos⁵, among others.

In this context, a significant endeavor has been undertaken by the EC, *Directorate-General for Research and Innovation*. In the year 2022, an extensive **survey of user needs** was conducted, with a primary focus on professionals in the **museum sector** [EC22]. This initiative was carried out as part of the activities designed for the establishment of the *European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage*. The aim was to gather the views of the CH stakeholders on this Commission's initiative, which is planned to be implemented with a set of specific calls in 2023-2025. This survey was able to receive replies from around 1000 CH professionals.

The results gathered are as follows:

- Confirm the sector's requirement for the establishment of a digital collaborative platform for CH, as nearly half of the respondents (46%) identify the absence of a digital collaboration platform with tools *tailored to the needs of CH professionals* as the primary challenge in the sector's digital transition.
- Affirm that the necessity extends beyond merely archiving digital data; a crucial objective is the availability of tools that support the integration and utilization of digital data in the day-to-day tasks of professionals. Digital interaction emerges as the highest priority among the respondents' tool requirements, encompassing tools for generating, sharing, and reusing interactive content on the Cloud (43.3%); tools for AI-assisted metadata enrichment to enhance interoperability of CH content (37%); tools for advanced interaction with the digital content on the Cloud (36.4%); and tools for analyzing, designing, and testing interactions with visitors (33.6%).
- The paramount importance of accessibility and user-friendliness has been emphasized; the new tools must be perceived as a service. It is crucial to ensure the collaborative development of these tools alongside the target users, facilitating extensive testing and verification before project

⁴ EC "ARIADNE PLUS" project and infrastructure: <https://ariadne-infrastructure.eu/>

⁵ EC "PARTHENOS" project: <https://www.parthenos-project.eu/>

completion. This approach supports users in their testing of the Cloud, contributing to a more effective implementation.

- Ensuring data and system interoperability is foundational for fostering synergies between the Cloud and other digital initiatives, addressing both legal and technical considerations.
- Consistently, the CH community underscores the importance of training, expertise development, and the establishment of best practices. A majority of respondents highlight the necessity for clear information regarding the benefits of the Cloud (61.5%) and training sessions on utilizing the Cloud (55.1%) as the primary support required for this initiative.
- Approximately 40% of the respondents express the requirement for IT support (40.8%), training in digital skills (38.9%), and the presence of an active user community (38.6%). Additionally, about one-third of the respondents emphasized the need for suitable IT equipment (32.3%).

This survey stands as a milestone achievement for endeavors related to digital support for CH management. In designing the survey for the CHANGES project, emphasis was placed on highlighting the specificities of CHANGES stakeholders, whose focus is predominantly on conservation and restoration, as opposed to the museum management orientation central to the community surveyed by the European Commission Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (EC DG R&I).

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The questionnaire

To gather more precise knowledge of CH stakeholders' needs concerning data encoding, integration, and processing, we decided to run a survey.

The goal of this survey was to gather structured information on current and future practices in digital CH, more in detail concerning the acquisition and use of digital data for diagnostic, knowledge, or fruition purposes (data acquisition/digitization, types of data gathered, encoding schema endorsed, archival practices, data analysis approaches).

The request to contribute to the survey was sent to the partners of PE5-Spoke5 and to other colleagues in Italy and the EU.

We received 32 completed surveys and 19 other surveys with an incomplete set of answers. Since some respondents were unsure about some topics mentioned in the questionnaire, we gave them the possibility to fill it incompletely, skipping the questions on which they had insufficient experience/knowledge. The total was 51 respondents.

The questions and the replies gathered are presented in the following.

Preliminary information

Q1: What is your professional domain/sector?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- GLAM (galleries, libraries, archives, and museums)
- Restoration/conservation
- Academia/research
- Other: ...

Comment: academics/researchers are the majority, but conservators + GLAM also have a good 30% share.

Q2: What is your job position (director, IT manager, conservator, researcher)?

Please write your answer here: ...

Researcher = 17
 Professor = 9
 Conservator = 9
 PhD student = 1
 Data steward = 1
 Engineer = 1
 Retired = 1

Digitization of artworks subject to study/conservation actions

Q3: Is the digitization of the subject of a study or conservation project already a standard preliminary phase in your practice?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- Under planning

Comment: the results show that a very strong majority of the experts sampled have already endorsed digitization

Q4: Digitization - which main representation media are you using?

Please choose **all** that apply:

- 2D images
- Panoramic images
- RTI
- 3D
- One of the previous, selected depending on the subject characteristics
- Other: ...

Comment: results show a prevalence of 2D and 3D, but also some expertise with RTI and Panoramic images. In the "Other" field, point clouds and hyperspectral data have been mentioned.

Q5: How digitized data are shared with your staff?

Please choose **all** that apply:

- File sharing
- Web-based repository
- Other: ...

Comment: results show a prevalence of file sharing (66%).

Q6: Do you have internal staff dedicated to 2D/3D digitization?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- No
- Yes, 2D digitization staff
- Yes, 3D digitization staff
- Yes, 2D and 3D digitization staff

Comment: results show a majority of labs having specialized staff (22 Yes and 18 No).

Q7: Digitization efforts so far managed with - staff:

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Own staff
- Support of external experts (academic or company)

Comment: support of external staff is still quite uncommon.

Q8: Digitization efforts so far managed with – funds:

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Own funds
- External funds

Comment: funds are in large majority not external (institutions are investing by themselves on digitization).

Digital encoding of diagnostic results

Q9: How do you produce/archive results of diagnostic investigations?

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Native digital files
- Scanned pdf
- Documents on paper
- Other: ...

Comment: In the majority of cases, diagnostic results are handled in digital formats.

Q10: Which data types are used?
(indicate as a percentage of the total)
The sum must equal 100.

Please write your answer(s) here:

- 2D images [...]
- 3D data [...]
- Graphs-pdf [...]
- Data tables (excel) [...]

Comment: predominance of 2D and 3D data.

- 2D images: 47% (on average)
- 3D data (CT, ...): 34% (on average)
- Graphs-pdf: 9% (on average)
- Data tables (excel): 10% (on average)

Data management

Q11: Your effective internal use of digitized data:

Please choose **all** that apply:

- To support artwork study
- To support artwork restoration
- To support dissemination

Comment: The results are well-balanced, with a notable emphasis on study and dissemination purposes.

Q12: Do you have a safely archived copy of the digitization campaigns' results?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes, for all of the campaigns
- Yes, for most of the campaigns
- Yes, for few of the campaigns
- No

Comment: archival is a common practice.

Q13: Do you need to save and preserve all data (raw data, intermediate results, final derived data) or just final results?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- All data
- Selected data
- Just final results
- It depends on the specific project
- Make a comment on your choice here: ...

Comments: a strong majority archives all data produced. In the "Make a comment..." field, the responders mentioned:

- Mostly the 3D models are permanently stored. Research intermediate data depend on the project.
- Preferable to keep all data for possible future work.
- Intermediate results are saved and preserved for potential reuse.

Q14: Have you considered physical and digital obsolescence issues and designed a policy?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- It is a work in progress

Comments: data obsolescence is taken into account only by one-third of the respondents (but many are planning to work on it).

Q15: How long digital data should be preserved, after the end of the project that has created them?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- < 5 years
- 5 to 10 years
- > 10 years
- It depends on the specific project

Comments: most respondents plan a very long preservation time.

Q16: what is your practical experience in terms of preservation?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Usually discontinued at the end of the project
- Usually lost after 5 years from the end of the project
- Usually lost after 10 years from the end of the project
- Usually preserved more than 10 years after the end of the project
- Make a comment on your choice here: ...

Comments: practical experience with data preservation is quite good (in most case >10Y). In the "Make a comment..." field, the responders mentioned:

- *It is getting better now, but we lost a lot.*
- *We should keep forever.*
- *Consider the problem of preserving the personal experiences, not just data (teaching to younger personnel)*

Q17: How do you support access to your digitized data?

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Plain storage of data (data files) on a personal machine
- Plain storage of data (data files) on a shared disk
- Archival in a digital library / repository, but just for internal use of the internal staff
- Publication in a publicly accessible repository (but with limitations, e.g. low resolution, partial data, ...)
- Grant public full access to all digital material (open data)
- Other: ...

Comments: archival in a digital library / repository is getting momentum, but the OpenData approach still far from becoming common.

Q18: Does your institution provide facilities for data storage?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- Planned

Comments: most institutions are providing storage facilities.

Q19: Does your institution provide facilities for data preservation/backup?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- Planned

Comments: most institutions are providing data preservation/backup facilities.

Q20: Are those facilities (storage/preservation/backup) implemented with:

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Internal resources
- Outsourced (commercial) services

Comments: a large majority uses internal resources (this follows the trend of trying to avoid commercial services in the CH domain).

Q21: Have you endorsed an open data policy?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- Planned

Comments: the future of open data seems to be bright, with a strong majority of people endorsing or planning to endorse it.

Q22: If Not to the question above, why?

Please write your answer here: ...

Answers:

- We work on works of art that pertain to public institutions and there are issues in the material's copyright.
- Not enough time.
- Not yet necessary.
- Actually, "don't know" should be added in this section. At university level I don't know if there is a policy on open data but usually the operations we carry out are for third party accounts and it is difficult for us to freely share the results.
- The property and accessibility to data is a sensible matter to be discussed with the possible owners of the artwork/facilities, the staff entrusted with the digitization task, and the possible funders.

Q23: Have you reused previously digitized data in other subsequent projects or activities?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes, frequently
- Yes, rarely
- Never

Comments: the percentage of reuse is very good.

Q24: Have you ever succeeded in monetizing some of the IP connected with digital material?

(e.g. selling reproduction rights or copies of the digitized results)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- Make a comment on your choice here: ...

Comments: this is also an expected result: the good practice of revenues from data is extremely rare. In the "Make a comment..." field, the responders mentioned:

- *All our data is made available under CC-BY, but we are increasingly receiving requests from companies to harvest our digital libraries to support commercial applications.*
- *We do not own a complete property of the materials, but we share them with the owners.*
- *Under French law, as public agents, everything we produce is shared freely.*

Data management – Semantic representation

Q25: How much would be important to couple the digitized visual data (3D, 2D, diagnostic results) with data characterizing the artwork (metadata), stored in a common and integrated archive?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Very important
- Important
- Slightly important

Comments: a strong majority requires visual data & related descriptive metadata.

Q26: Do you have plans to store also paradata (data characterizing how the digitized data was gathered and processed) together with the digitized assets?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

Comments: here the majority is less strong.

Q27: Data enrichment: would you be willing to spend resources (time and staff) in enriching manually the data with metadata and paradata?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

Comments: respondents are largely willing to invest in data enrichment.

Q28: Are you interested in applying **reasoning over metadata** (adopting approaches based on CIDOC-CRM and linked data) or are you just interested in using the digitized data per se?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Reasoning over metadata
- Just using digitized data
- Make a comment on your choice here: ...

Comments: only slightly more than 50% are willing to apply reasoning over metadata (the major plus of the CIDOC-CRM approach). In the "Make a comment..." field, the responders mentioned:

- *It is an approach more adequate for younger specialists*

Services for data analysis

Q29: Are you currently using a data analysis systems/software?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- Under planning

Comments: the sum of the ones using or planning is slightly more than the ones not using; there is wide space for improvement.

Q30: If Yes to the question above, please choose all that apply and provide a comment:

- Proprietary
- Commercial
- Shared/open source

Indicate the names of the system(s) you use: ...

Comments: results are quite balanced. In the "Make a comment..." field, the responders mentioned:

- Proprietary (data analysis, metashape)
- Commercial (Agisoft Photoscan; Excel, Plug-ins for Grasshopper; Matlab)
- Shared/open source (MeshLab, 3DHOP; MeshLab, 3DHOP, CloudCompare; XRF analysis software; Gephi)

Q31: Types of actions/functionalities a tool for data storage and analysis should support (indicate your preferences):

- **Data visualization (interactive)**
– viz, zoom, panning, ...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Slightly important
- Important
- Very important

Comments: by far the most requested feature.

- **Web-based visualization, shared**

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Slightly important
- Important
- Very important

Comments: web visualization is important to respondents, but less so than other features.

- **Common and congruent graphics user interface for all the data types (2D/3D)**

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Slightly important
- Important
- Very important

Comments: the large majority of the respondents consider it very important to have a congruent graphics user interface for different data.

- Computation of **measures** on digital representations

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Slightly important
- Important
- Very important

Comments: interactive measurement tools are considered very important, too.

- Cut-through sections

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Slightly important
- Important
- Very important

Comments: sections are important to respondents, but less so than other features.

- **Semantic data** ingestions (metadata, paradata)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Slightly important
- Important
- Very important

Comments: semantic data ingestion is important to respondents, but the number of people who consider it very important is equal to the number of those who consider it not very important

- **Annotation** over 2D/3D representations, to store comments or knowledge

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Slightly important
- Important
- Very important

Comments: data annotation is important to respondents, but less so than other features.

Q32: About the **annotations** over 2D/3D representations that a tool for data storage and analysis should support, what are the **types of annotations requested – spatiality:**

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Point
- Lines
- Regions

Comments: point and area annotations are the most requested.

Q33: About the **annotations** over 2D/3D representations that a tool for data storage and analysis should support, what are the **types of annotations requested – content:**

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Text
- Images
- Web Links
- Sound/Voice

Comments: text and images still dominate the scene, web links are also important, while audio contents are quite optional.

Q34: Other possible useful functionalities?

Please write your answer here: ...

Answers:

- Annotation allowing to make evident the links between different parts of the same model connected by a common story (e.g., sculpture components restored in ancient times by the same person/group).
- Annotations representing URLs pointing to documents (Excel reports with measurements, PDFs, etc.)
- It would be very useful to provide a scripting language extension so that we can integrate specialized computations on 3D mesh models. I mostly use MeshLab for visualization and point picking and everything else is being processed with GNU Octave and C++. It would be nice to be able to merge my octave functions into meshlab as external scripts/functions. Of course, python would work too if it's easier to integrate to.
- Capacity to incorporate Linked Data identifiers and to be exported in Linked Data formats, as a way to connect the resources to the larger LD ecosystem on the basis of informal (user-provided?) annotations as well as metadata.
- Possible animation of the 2D or 3D object depending on the type of data acquired.

Q35: In case CHANGES will provide free-use services, will you **accept to be monitored** while using the tools? (e.g. number of users downloading and using an app or a digitized model, etc). All of this ensuring privacy protection.

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- Make a comment on your choice here: ...

Comments: potential users are not scared to be monitored. In the "Make a comment..." field, the responders mentioned:

- *yes, as long as the monitoring is completely transparent. i.e. users can also see the aggregated anonymized data.*

Fruition and multimedia content creation

Q36: Does your institution/staff have experience with the **production of multimedia content**, as a by-product of an investigation project (e.g. for dissemination purposes)?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- No
- Yes, rarely
- Yes, frequently

Comment: nice to see that nearly all respondents have at least some experience

Q37: This multimedia content is usually designed:

Please choose **all that apply**:

- To be part of a museum exposition
- For web dissemination
- Other: ...

Comment: web dissemination is gaining momentum. In the "Other" field, the responders mentioned:

- For scientific presentations at conferences and events (3)
- For documentation
- For open air tourism
- To be used by archaeologists to review field investigations

Q38: Your experience so far with multimedia content production:

Please choose **all** that apply:

- **Passive content** design/creation (animations, videos, slide-based presentations)
- **Interactive installations** design/creation (interactive kiosks, VR, etc.)

Comments: passive content is largely the most common option.

Q39: Design and implementation of multimedia content:

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Done by yourself
- With support of a private company
- With support of an academic partner

Comments: half of the polled are able to design and develop multimedia content without any external support.

Results:

- Done by yourself: 54% (in avg)
- With support of a private company: 15% (in avg)
- With support of an academic partner: 31% (in avg)

Q40: Have you archived/stored for preservation purposes the fruition material you have created up to now?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- No
- Yes, rarely
- Yes, frequently
- Yes, always

Comments: the percentage of people not preserving fruition material is minimal, but remains consistent.

Q41: Which type of permanent preservation policy have you endorsed?

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Copy of the installation
- Video(s) showing the capabilities and user interaction
- Other: ...

Comments: to store a backup copy of the installation is the favorite option. In the "Other" field, the responders mentioned:

- *Data exports in flat or interoperable formats*
- *Planned*
- *None*

Tab. 1 Questions, answers options, and replies gathered through the survey on CH stakeholders' needs concerning data encoding, integration, and processing.

Experience gathered and concluding remarks

The survey results indicate that the sampled individuals possess a solid background in utilizing digital media. Furthermore, there is potential for improving the adoption of these resources. Importantly, the functionalities planned for the digital tool(s) align well with the requirements and expectations of the stakeholders.

A detailed comment on the replies gathered follows.

Survey results – Some comments

Digitization of artworks subject to study/conservation actions

The survey shows that the experts sampled have already endorsed **digitization**; the community is very well-oriented towards digital CH and, thus, a very good asset for designing and assessing digital tools. The polled profiles mostly use 2D and 3D **data types**, aligning with expectations. It is noteworthy that the preference for 3D is relatively close to that of 2D images among our stakeholders. Respondents also demonstrate proficiency with Reflectance Transformation Imaging (RTI) and panoramic images. Notably, respondents also mentioned point clouds and hyperspectral data.

Concerning the **digitization** task, the survey results show that a majority of institutions have specialized **staff** (that is good news, since the presence of staff with solid experience in digital media is key to success for the use of new digital tools). Results also demonstrate that support of external staff is still quite uncommon, possibly due to the related cost (in the case of industrial collaborations). Moreover, **funds for digitization** are in large majority not external (institutions are investing their own resources to perform digitization), but it is unclear if this is subsidized by money coming from research projects.

Digital encoding of diagnostic results

According to the survey, in most cases, diagnostic results (mostly 2D and 3D data) are managed in **digital format** (again good news, demonstrating that the transition towards digital CH is in progress).

Data management

The survey shows that particular attention is given to data archiving. **Data archival** is a common practice, and a strong majority archives **all data produced** (raw and final), **for long periods** (in most cases >10Y). Despite that, **data obsolescence** is taken into account only by one-third of the respondents (but many are planning to work on it soon).

Concerning **data storage, preservation, and backup**, most institutions are providing such facilities (but this is mostly the context of research institutions rather than the one of cultural institutions). These facilities are often implemented with internal resources (this follows the trend of trying to avoid commercial services in the CH domain).

To support **access to digitized data**, the archival in a digital library or repository is gaining momentum, but the OpenData approach is still far from becoming common. Nevertheless, the future of **open data** seems to be bright, with a strong majority of respondents endorsing or planning to endorse it.

Finally, other interesting responses state that digitized data are mainly used for study and dissemination **purposes**; the **reuse** of previously digitized data in other subsequent projects or activities is a common practice; and the practice of **generating revenue** from these data is exceptionally uncommon.

Data management – Semantic representation

A strong majority of the sampled experts require that visual data be associated with their descriptive **metadata** in a common and integrated archive, while the majority of those also requiring **paradata** is less strong (around 30% are not planning to add paradata). Some of this resistance could also be due to the usually complex and messy interfaces for inserting paradata.

If on one hand respondents are largely willing to **invest resources** (time and staff) in **data enrichment**, on the other hand only slightly more than 50% of them are willing to apply **reasoning over metadata** (the major plus of the CIDOC-CRM approach).

Services for data analysis

From the survey result that the sum of the respondents who are using or planning to use a data **analysis SW** is approximately equal to the ones not using (so, there is wide space for improvement in the adoption and use of data analysis SW). The ecosystem of the SW used for data analysis is very heterogeneous, including **open-source solutions** (MeshLab, 3DHOP, CloudCompare, Gephi) **and not** (Agisoft Metashape, MathWorks Matlab, Microsoft Excel, Grasshopper 3D).

Concerning the types of actions or **functionalities that a tool for data storage and analysis should support**, a positive observation is that a substantial majority of respondents deem all the proposed features as important, indicating a widespread consensus on the significance of these attributes. In particular, **interactive data visualization**, **a common and congruent graphics user interface** for all the data types (2D/3D), and **computation of measures** on digital representations, are considered by the great majority of the respondents three very important features; **web-based visualization**, producing **cut-through sections**, and the **possibility to annotate** 2D/3D representations to store comments or knowledge are also perceived as three **important** feature (but slightly less than the three previous features); finally, **semantic data ingestions** (metadata, paradata) is also considered an important feature, but in this case the number of people who consider it very important is equal to the number of those who consider it not very important (7 vs 8).

About the **annotations** over 2D/3D representations that a tool for data storage and analysis should **support**, point-wise and region-wise annotations are the preferred modalities; while concerning the requested **annotation content type**, the results show a preference for text and images, slightly less for web links, while only few respondents would like to see voice-based annotations.

Finally, is nice to see that potential users are not scared to be monitored while using the tools provided by the CHANGES project. This is an important issue (since only **monitoring** activities allows SW

developers to gather data on the effective usage of the different tools) and, thus, a critical query for our potential users.

Fruition and multimedia content creation

Nearly all the survey respondents have at least some experience with the **production of multimedia content** as a by-product of an investigation project. These multimedia contents are in prevalence **passive media** (such as animations or videos), **developed by themselves**, and produced **for web dissemination** rather than to be part of a museum exhibition (this is probably because the majority of respondents are academic rather than museum staff).

The fruition material created is usually **archived/stored for preservation** purposes, mostly through a copy of the installation, while the simple option of grabbing videos and preserving them is adopted in only a few cases. The percentage of respondents not preserving or preserving only sometimes the fruition multimedia material is small but remains consistent.

How the survey steers the design of tools in Changes – Spoke 5 – WP5

CHANGES-Spoke 5-WP5 aims at developing innovative digital technologies to support data-driven research in the CH domain, enabling a new paradigm for data collection, integration, processing, visualization, annotation, and documentation. In this context, this survey has been run to investigate CH stakeholders' needs and gather structured information on current and future practices in digital CH.

The good participation of the contacted experts was a first and very positive sign of interest in the topics addressed. But the community involvement and commitment also emerge from some survey responses, for example by the fact that the great majority of the institutions are investing their funds in digitization (85%), are willing to invest time and personnel resources in data semantic enrichment (83%), and would also be willing to be monitored while using the new tools provided by the project (83%).

The survey shows a community very well-oriented towards digital CH, used to work with digital data (even in 3D format) and specialized (digitization) staff, already aware of the best practices regarding data management (archival, preservation, access), and with some experience in the production of dissemination content (as a by-product of an investigation project). This picture of the CH community is very positive since the presence of experience on digital media is key to success for the use and evaluation of new digital tools (the primary goal of WP5).

New digital tools should be primarily focused on implementing services for data analysis, since almost 50% of respondents admit they are not using or planning to use data analysis software. From this, it directly follows that there is wide space for improvement in the adoption and use of data analysis services. In this regard, the survey helps in steering the design effort of WP5, providing a list of priorities regarding the features that the developed tools should support (interactive visualization and data inspection tools, before others) and other interesting insights (e.g., the fact that semantic data ingestions, still considered important, just follow interfaces usability among respondents).

The survey also underlines the importance of new tools and services widely accessible for users and institutions (open source or at least non-commercial), web-oriented to enable data accessibility (endorsing open access), integrated to support crosslink information (metadata and paradata), and

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with a long-term vision (to support data storage, preservation, and backup, dealing with data obsolescence).

Finally, since it has been manifested the great importance of reusing digital data for dissemination purposes, the identikit of new digital tools should also include features aimed at the creation of multimedia content as a by-product of an investigation project (and therefore capable of managing complex scientific data), which can be directly used by non-specialized users (easy to use) and able to create content contents accessible beyond classic museum uses (web-oriented).

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